

A NOTE ON THE MOVEMENT OF CAMPHOR ON WATER

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Raleigh (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1890, A, 47, 364) found that to stop the motion of camphor on water, a lowering of surface tension by 16 dynes was required. This phenomenon has been studied by a number of other investigators (Miss Pockels, *Nature*, 1891, 43, 437 ; Ramdas, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1926, 1, 1). Edwards (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 144), Goppert (*Z. Physik*, 1919, 20, 78) and others have shown that other organic substances also behave in a similar manner. An attempt has been made in this paper to gain some definite information on the subject, with reference to the size and shape of the moving piece of camphor and also the effect of temperature and pressure.

The camphor used in these experiments was a pure synthetic one from B. D. H. having m. p. of 175°.

The motion of camphor on water could be resolved into two types : (1) rotatory in which the particles swim round their own axes at a rapid rate, and (2) translatory in which the particles swim around the trough of water keeping close to the walls of the vessel. The first type of motion is always observed with smaller particles, while the bigger ones move round, the former type of motion being almost absent. The behaviour of a tiny speck of camphor on a drop of water, if viewed under the microscope, is interesting. At first the edges of the crystal vanish and the particle assumes a smooth rounded shape. As the edges go off, the particle tends to move in the opposite direction. The edges and the corners of the crystal are more susceptible to volatilisation than the mass. The resultant of a series of recoil forces due to this volatilisation should be acting as a couple at the ends producing a rotatory motion. A simple analogous experiment with solid carbon dioxide illustrates the point.

Specks of solid carbon dioxide, loosely held together (but not compressed), if thrown in a trough of water, float on it and as carbon dioxide rapidly sublimates, the specks rotate violently. There is no translatory motion.

Next, pieces of camphor 2 (mm. thickness) of various geometrical shapes were tried. Squares of 1 cm. side, circular pieces of 1 cm. diameter, and crescent shaped pieces of 1 cm. chord were made by pressing into shape in wooden moulds. Thus the perimeter was varied. All of them, except the crescent shaped one, exhibited more of translatory motion than rotatory one. The crescent shaped pieces rotated violently, and swam around only when the corners were blunt due to volatilisation. They did not show motion away from the concave side as claimed by Ramdas (*loc. cit.*). In all these experiments water was absolutely free from grease or any speck of camphor other than the one under observation. Every time an experiment was performed, fresh water was used.

Though in all these pieces the perimeter was different from one another, all of them at 25° swam with an average velocity of 3.5 cm. per second. Pieces pressed hard into spherical shapes showed no motion at all. But those pressed

between non-greasy and dry fingers, so that they were flat, with the central portion more compressed than the edges, swam with greater velocity than those made in the press under pressure. They had an average velocity of 4.6 cm. per second. The loose edges having greater chances of volatilisation are responsible for this increased velocity. Hence in the following experiments only such pieces were taken. The average velocity in these experiments was calculated from the number of times the circumference of the trough was traversed in 5 minutes; troughs of different diameters were also used.

Temperature.—Experiments were performed at a constant temperature in a thermostat having accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The following table shows the effect of temperature on the motion of camphor.

TABLE I

Temp.	15°	25°	30°	40°
Velocity (cm./sec.)	1.0	4.6	7.0	There is only feeble rotatory motion but no translatory motion.

Pressure.—Experiments were next conducted under the cover of a bell jar attached to a suction pump and a vacuum gauge. The enclosure was kept at various pressures and the behaviour of camphor was observed. After each observation the water was changed and the bell jar cleaned and kept exposed to air for a considerable length of time to drive off the smell of camphor inside it. The results are given in Table II.

Table II

Temp. = 25°.

Pressure. (cm.)		76	56	44	39
Velocity (cm./sec.)		4.3	2.4	2.1	1.9

The motion decreased with lowering of air pressure, the rate of fall was, however, far from being proportional. A bell jar containing vapour of camphor sublimed into it was brought over the trough of water on which the camphor was moving. The motion was at once arrested and the piece of camphor stopped moving.

From the above experiments it is clear that the perimeter or the geometrical shape of the piece of camphor does not seem to be important. The rotatory motion is due to the volatilisation of camphor giving rise to a couple acting on the piece.

Miss Pockels (*loc cit.*) explains the movement of camphor on water as due to the greater insolubility of surface than that in the bulk of the solvent and consequent changes in surface tension. This is in consonance with the thermodynamically derived equation of Gibbs, if one identifies the surface concentration with the phenomenon of adsorption. A Langmuir-Taylor type of surface forces on water might be imagined with the possibility of lateral shift of the adsorbed molecule of camphor vapour to a final position of minimum energy. The lateral shift of the adsorbed molecule of camphor vapour produces a recoil on the main piece giving it a translatory motion.

At 40° and above, the process of evaporation of water is rapid and molecules of water at the surface evaporate away rapidly leaving a surface which is not capable of imparting any lateral shift to the adsorbed molecules. Hence the result in Table I. As could be expected from this reasoning, the activity of camphor in water is less when the vessel is evacuated, since even in this case the evaporation of the more active surface molecules leaves a surface with poor capacity for adsorption. Further saturated vapour of camphor, as in the bell jar experiment, arrests the motion of camphor in a striking manner. This is due to the surface of water being saturated at once with camphor vapour and hence no chance for a lateral shift occurs.

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